

USING INTERACTIVE MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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This is particularly true in such English-speaking countries as Australia, USA, Canada, and the United Kingdom. Majority of the published research on the effectiveness of media and technology in language instruction is encouraging. Among other benefits, new technologies present opportunities to accomplish various instructional goals (e.g., integrated language skills, critical thinking, and cooperative skills). They may also be responsive to different learning styles (e.g., auditory, visual, tangible). The practice of incorporating multi-media and computer technology into language instruction opens up a new horizon for teachers of English language to improve the overall quality of language instruction. The modern communicatively approach teaching prepares pupils to use foreign languages in real-life conditions. Use of interactive multimedia technologies in communicative teaching foreign language considerably raises quality of giving material of a lesson and efficiency of mastering of this material by pupils. As practice shows, use and introduction of modern technologies, the multimedia equipment enriches the maintenance of educational process, raises motivation of pupils to learn English language and at the same time close cooperation between teacher and pupils is achieved. Multimedia technologies mean use of such audiovisual and interactive tutorials as:

- 1) Software (multimedia disks, presentations, audio and video clips. resources of the Internet);
- 2) Hardware (personal computer (PC), audio - video - equipment, multimedia projector, interactive board or smart board).

Video courses, being good addition to the lesson maintenance, can introduce sociocultural realias: a mimicry and gestures, clothes, surrounding conditions.

Besides, on the basis of these video courses, teacher can set various role-play games and organise discussions, debates for the purpose of repetition of the passed lexical material. Audiocassettes and disks which are an obligatory component of modern foreign language teaching, contain records of texts and tasks for audition, songs, rhymes, exercises which are an effective method of working on a pronunciation. Records are recorded by professional sound technicians with participation of specially invited actors - of native speakers. Nowadays there is a set of multimedia tutorials, such as interactive courses “Tell me more”, “English: a way to perfection”, children’s encyclopaedias (for example: “Encyclopaedia Britannica”), etc. They are calculated on training speech activities: reading, writing, listening, and speaking; they also contain explanation and repetition of a various grammatical material with corresponding tasks and exercises, as for independent training, and work in a group. If teacher can choose appropriate materials correctly necessary to pupils and use it in the form accessible to pupils, both pupils and teacher will benefit a lot.

Teacher can use lesson plans created independently, for example, on Power Point presentation. Children are involved in creative research process, as all projects are the individual-focused kind of work and as they write about themselves, their family, their house, and hobbies. By preparation of projects they study themes interesting to write, rummage in directories, talk to other people, search for photos and drawings even do audio and video recordings independently.

The list of used literature:

1. Emig, J. Writing as a Mode of Learning // College Composition and Communication, 1977. - 28 (2).
2. Evans, V. Successful Writing. Proficiency Student’s Book. - Express Publishing, 1998.
3. Evans, V. Successful Writing. Upper-Intermediate Student’s Book. - Express Publishing, 2004.